

SOCIAL SCIENCES

ETHICAL AND SOCIAL CHALLENGES OF DIGITAL REALITY: RISKS ASSOCIATED WITH THE ONLINE ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

The 21st century is the era of globalization, where the world is becoming increasingly “open” to interactions, national boundaries are weakening, and this is primarily due to digital reality, which has simplified numerous processes over time, while at the same time generating a considerable number of negative consequences.

Digital reality entails universal computerization, cybernetization, the free circulation of information in society, and the ability to provide precise and comprehensive responses to any information request from the public. However, alongside its many advantages, it also brings challenges and risks. With the advancement of digital reality, numerous ethical and social challenges arise, which are directly linked to the online environment and its inherent dangers.

This paper examines the ethical and social challenges of digital reality in Georgia, including the risks associated with the online environment, the current situation, and its specific features. Proposes necessary solutions to overcome the problems of digital reality.

Keywords: Digital Reality, Digital Ethics, Digital Security

Introduction. Today, the world lives in a digital era. As of February 2025, the number of internet users worldwide amounted to 5.56 billion, representing 67.9 percent of the global population. Of these, 5.24 billion people, 63.9 percent of the world’s population, were social media users [1]. The rapidly evolving technological environment, along with new opportunities, also generates challenges, giving rise to various ethical and social issues directly linked to the digital environment and the risks it entails. Digital reality offers vast opportunities, but it also requires digital ethics, regulations, and enhancing user awareness to ensure that the online environment is safe, fair, and beneficial for society.

Georgia is a small country, but this has its advantages, as adapting to new realities can be more straightforward. The introduction of modern digital technologies and securing a respectable position in the global information space are considered a priority task for the country. Successfully addressing this task is of decisive importance for achieving strategic objectives such as establishing a democratic, free, and rule-of-law state, fostering the development of civil society, ensuring national security, protecting human rights, and combating poverty, corruption, extremism, and terrorism [2].

Digital reality is developing rapidly in Georgia, but along with the arising risks and ethical problems that also exist in other countries. Though in Georgia, they acquire certain local specificities. Digital ethics is becoming particularly relevant in Georgia, as the use of online banking services, social networks, state services, and e-commerce models is steadily increasing [3].

Research Aim and Objectives. The primary aim of this study is to examine the risks associated with the online environment and the ethical and social challenges of digital reality, to identify the current situation

and its specific characteristics in Georgia, and to develop necessary solutions, precise conclusions, and recommendations for overcoming the problems of digital reality.

Research Methodology. During the research, relevant scientific literature and studies were examined, a comparative analysis of collected materials and statistical data was conducted, and certain conclusions and recommendations were developed.

Discussion/Results. In the modern world, one of the most significant challenges of digital reality is digital ethics. That is a system of ethical principles and norms that define how we should act responsibly in the digital environment - as individuals, companies, and states. Digital ethics encompasses the protection of personal data, transparency of information, norms of online behavior, and maintaining a balance between digital reality and human values.

Among the challenges of digital ethics is the ethical use of Big Data and artificial intelligence, hate speech and disinformation, highlighting the responsibility of platforms to limit the spread of false information. Another issue is digital inequality, as not everyone has equal access to the internet and digital services, thereby deepening social inequality. The protection of intellectual property also poses a challenge, as in the digital world, safeguarding authors’ rights is challenging. Ethical challenges further include the protection of children and vulnerable groups online, as well as the influence of global platforms on local culture and politics. The protection of personal data occupies a significant place among ethical challenges, as companies and platforms often collect information about users, including their location, behaviors, and interests. It is noteworthy that data protection is one of the pressing challenges of the modern world, raising the

ethical question of how transparently and fairly this information is used.

Every user leaves a digital footprint in the virtual world. A digital footprint is online information about an individual, published either by the person themselves or by others, deliberately or unintentionally. That also includes information about websites visited and emails sent by the individual. The volume of a digital footprint grows in proportion to user activity. Since the digital trace remains online for a long time and is accessible to strangers, there is a risk that unscrupulous actors may misuse the published information for other purposes [4].

The main principles of digital ethics are as follows:

- ✓ **Respect for Privacy:** It is ethically unacceptable to collect or disseminate user data without consent
- ✓ **Transparency:** Users must be informed about how their data is being used
- ✓ **Security:** User data must be protected against cyber threats
- ✓ **Fairness and Equality:** Technologies should not reinforce social inequality or discrimination
- ✓ **Responsibility:** Accountability for actions in the online space is essential
- ✓ **Digital Well-being:** Technologies should not harm human mental or physical health (e.g., excessive dependence, bullying).

Digital ethics serves as a connecting link between technology and human values, teaching us how to use digital tools in a way that harmonizes innovation, security, and fairness.

In Georgia, with respect to digital inequality, it is noteworthy that access to the internet and technologies differs sharply between urban and rural areas. Moreover, families with low incomes face difficulties in acquiring technologies, and children often fall behind their peers in terms of online education. Regarding media and platform responsibility, it is noteworthy that in Georgia, Facebook and other social networks represent the primary sources of information, yet control over disinformation and hate speech remains weak. On the other hand, concerning monitoring and censorship, excessive surveillance of internet activity by the authorities may pose a threat to personal freedoms and freedom of expression. Local specificities also characterize cultural influence: foreign platforms often displace local cultural content, and global trends tend to be more popular among young people than the national cultural sphere [5].

The most significant risks associated with digital reality in Georgia are:

1. **Cybersecurity and Cyber Fraud:** Fraudulent schemes connected to banks, online shops, and social networks (such as phishing, fake links, and malicious SMS messages) are standard, while many citizens still lack sufficient knowledge to protect their personal data.
2. **Online Disinformation and Propaganda:** Particularly in relation to political and public life, where social networks are frequently used to polarize society. Fake news spreads rapidly on Facebook, Telegram, and TikTok.

3. **Personal Data Protection:** Many online services operating in Georgia, such as e-commerce platforms and state portals, lack strict data protection standards, making it easy for citizens' personal information to fall into the hands of third parties.

4. **Risks of Online Shopping:** Fraudulent websites, non-transparent pricing, and mismatches in product quality are common, while consumer rights in the online sphere are still inadequately protected.

5. **Cyberbullying and Digital Violence:** Hate speech, bullying, and the dissemination of personal photos/videos are especially prevalent among adolescents. Legal mechanisms in this area remain underdeveloped, while digital awareness is still at a low level.

In the Georgian context, regarding respect for privacy, it is noteworthy that the National Agency of Public Registry stores and transfers citizens' data only under conditions defined by law. The ethical challenge here lies in the fact that there are cases when citizens' personal data, such as residential address, mobile phone number, and others, become easily accessible in public databases. In this case, the principle of digital ethics implies data minimization, meaning the collection and protection of only the information that is strictly necessary.

As for transparency, security, as well as fairness and equality, although banks notify customers about the purposes for which their personal data is used, the operation of algorithms is not fully transparent. Accordingly, an ethical approach would be to develop rules that are easily understandable for users. In terms of security, online banking and payment systems in Georgia already employ two-factor authentication, a practice based on the principle of digital ethics, maximizing the protection of users' financial and personal data. Regarding fairness and equality, it is noteworthy that using payment terminals and online banking remains difficult for seniors and persons with disabilities. In this case, digital ethics requires inclusive design, developing services in a way that ensures accessibility for everyone.

A particular challenge in Georgia concerns the direction of digital well-being. Facebook and TikTok are especially popular in the country. Among young people, cyberbullying and hate speech are frequent, and here the ethical principle is the joint obligation of platforms and schools to safeguard the psychological well-being of children [6].

Currently, several laws in Georgia address digital security issues. These include: the National Cybersecurity Strategy of Georgia for 2021–2024 and its Action Plan [7]; the new Law of Georgia on Personal Data Protection, which entered into force on March 1, 2024 - a GDPR-like framework that defines rules of data processing, security standards, and the requirement to appoint a data protection officer [8]; and the Law of Georgia on Copyright and Related Rights [9], which regulates copyright (in the creation and use of works of science, literature, and art), related rights (relationships concerning performers, producers of phonograms/videos, and broadcasting organizations), and the rights of database creators.

To address the challenges of digital reality, Georgia should expand regulations in several directions, in particular:

1. In the field of cybersecurity and online fraud.

At the state level, it is advisable to strengthen the national cybersecurity strategy and expand the functionality of the Computer Emergency Response Team (CERT). In banking and online services, two-factor authentication and informing users about risks should be mandatory. While for society at large, cyber hygiene campaigns must be intensified (e.g., how to identify phishing, how to protect passwords, etc.).

2. In the field of disinformation and propaganda. The teaching of media literacy and digital citizenship elements in schools and higher education institutions should be further reinforced to develop critical thinking. At the same time, it is essential to strengthen support for fact-checking platforms (e.g., FactCheck.ge) and to enhance cooperation with social media platforms for the rapid identification of fake accounts and control of hate speech.

3. In the field of personal data protection. It is necessary to tighten regulations, ensure more active enforcement of the law, strengthen the authority of data protection officers, and increase corporate accountability. Local businesses must adopt clear policies on the use of customer data. Finally, raising citizens' awareness is crucial, through simple instructions and guidelines on how to limit the sharing of personal information online.

4. In the field of digital inequality. Expanding internet infrastructure in rural regions and providing affordable internet packages to low-income households are essential. Social programs should be implemented to improve access to technology, for example, the Ministry of Education could supply budget laptops/tablets to socially vulnerable families. Finally, training and online education programs are necessary, particularly for the older generation, to enable them to use digital services.

5. In the field of cyberbullying and digital violence. It is advisable to strengthen the legal framework by adopting clear laws against cyberbullying and digital violence. At the same time, awareness-raising and education in schools are crucial, so that children and parents are informed on how to protect themselves in the online space. Finally, it is necessary to establish support services and mobilize specialized platforms where victims can receive legal and psychological assistance.

As for resolving ethical dilemmas, maintaining balance is essential in every area, in particular: Freedom of expression vs. disinformation control – regulations should be developed that prevent harmful content but do not restrict free expression; Privacy vs. security – the state must find a balance between protecting citizens and avoiding excessive surveillance; Global platforms vs. local culture – more support is needed for the development of Georgian-language content.

Conclusion

Digital reality offers vast opportunities, but it is also associated with ethical and social challenges and risks. The capabilities of modern technology exacerbate these threats even further. However, it is impossible to eliminate such risks. It is possible to reduce them significantly. That requires digital ethics, regulations, and the enhancement of user awareness to ensure that the online environment is safe, fair, and beneficial for society.

To overcome the problems of digital reality in Georgia, multifaceted cooperation is essential. Specifically, the state must develop strategies and regulations; businesses must ensure data protection and user safety; the education system must provide digital literacy training at all levels of education; and, finally, society must demonstrate readiness to remain informed and responsible.

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